

English Pronunciation, Intonation, and Accent Reduction for Japanese Speakers: A Book Review

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- Abstract : The purpose of this study was to review the book English Pronunciation, Intonation, and Accent Reduction for Japanese Speakers. This research applied the library research method to review a book related to techniques in teaching English pronunciation. Data were prepared and analyzed using data reduction, data display, and concluding. The review result of this research was the book is recommended and appropriate as new pronunciation guides and online courses, and learn tips and techniques for teaching and learning English pronunciation, intonation, and accent reduction. The advantage of this book is a practical and user-friendly guide that provides specific advice and exercises to help Japanese speakers improve their English pronunciation. The writer also gives applications and online links related to the material. The book is designed specifically for Japanese speakers, so it may not be as helpful for learners from other language backgrounds. This book may be too technical for readers who do not have a background in phonetics or linguistics. It is also more focused on pronunciation aspects rather than overall language acquisition, so the readers may need to seek other sources to strengthen their English language skills as a whole.
- Keywords : *book review, pronunciation, English sounds*
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1. Introduction

A teacher is one of the important components in the teaching and learning process. Teachers play the most important role and they can overcome or minimize the problem faced by students. The success of the English learning process depends on the teacher as the model in the classroom, especially in learning pronunciation. According to Harmer (2001), good teacher cares more about their students' learning than they do about their own teaching. In this case, a teacher has to play an important role to develop students' pronunciation. As Brown (2001) said, there are five roles of teachers in teaching English.

First is the teacher as a controller. It is demanded to be able to control what the students do when they should speak and what language forms they should use. Second, the teacher is a director. In the classroom interactive, the teacher is like a conductor of an orchestra or a director of drama. It means that the teacher keeps the learning process running smoothly and efficiently. Third, the teacher is a manager. The teacher plans lessons and modules and courses so that the objectives of teaching and learning can be achieved. Next, the teacher is a facilitator. It means the teacher facilitates the process of learning, making learning easier for students, helping them to clear away roadblocks, finding shortcuts, and negotiating rough terrain. The last is the teacher as a resource, the teacher advises and council the students, when they have something to ask.

In the teaching and learning process, the teachers can use alternative effective techniques, especially techniques in teaching pronunciation. According to Brown (2001), "Technique is a preparation of activities in learning to achieve the desired learning objectives." Teaching technique is needed to achieve teaching-learning purposes. It makes learning easier, more fun, and more effective in the classroom. Therefore, the teacher should consider suitable techniques teaching for students.

Based on Hewings said there are three main ways of teaching pronunciation (Hewings, 1993). The first is to be aware of the likely pronunciation difficulties of students with particular first language groups and prepare activities that will focus on these problems. Next, if possible, diagnose your students' pronunciation weaknesses and plan activities that focus on these. The last, look at the syllabus in the course book you are using and identify which parts lend themselves to work on particular areas of pronunciation.

Teaching pronunciation is significant because it is one of the language components in English that espouse the process of language learning which needs to be paid attention to language training. According to Basuki (2016), "Through pronunciation mastery, one's speaking will be fluent, other people will be easy to understand it, or in the other word, people will not understand when the speaker pronounces incorrectly." In addition, pronunciation plays a pivotal role in language learning.

Pronunciation skill is important and helps students to speak fluently because they related to oral communication. Based on Basuki (2018) stated, "Having good mastery of grammar and vocabulary is not more important than having a good mastery of pronunciation for those who want to speak and deliver their ideas orally." It means that people see a person's English ability from their pronunciation for the first. Also supported by Khan (2019), "One of the main goals of learners and teachers while learning and teaching the English language is to acquire native-like proficiency, the first thing that is noticed is the pronunciation of the target language, which creates a positive impression about the competence of speaker." Indeed,

when a speaker is speaking English, so the listener can identify how dependable pronunciation the person has.

Based on the background above, the teacher's problem based on several journals was that English teachers seldom correct students' pronunciation for several reasons. According to Taqiyuddin (2021), teachers are still less to apply the techniques to correct and improve students' pronunciation, so not all of the students practice their pronunciation skills. Another source was English teachers do not teach specifically to any of the features of pronunciation such as diphthongs, phonemes, etc. Based on Yuniartiningasih (2020), "The teacher does not teach those features of English pronunciation, just directly to the form of the sound."

In this research, the researcher analyzed focused on a review of a book under the title "English Pronunciation, Intonation, and Accent Reduction for Japanese Speakers". The writer's book is Peggy Tharpe published by American Pronunciation Coach, 2021. This book has not been reviewed since it is the latest book in 2021, so it requires reviewing the teacher's technique in teaching English pronunciation.

2. Methods

2.1. Design

This research used descriptive qualitative research and the type of research used was library research thesis. It is because this research analyzed and made a description of teaching pronunciation with a review of a book. The researcher would like to analyze the data from a main book and comparison with another book. The research focused on analyzing the book reviews with the main book according to Table 1.

Table 1. Books Reviewed in this Study

Author	Peggy Tharpe M.A TESOL	
Book Title	English Pronunciation, Intonation, and Accent Reduction For Japanese Speakers	
Page	213	
Publisher	American Pronunciaton Coach	
Publication date	May 24, 2021	
Language	English	
ASIN	B095SZWD2F	

Table 2. The Comparison of a Main Book

Author	Charles W. Kreidler	
Book Title	The Pronunciation of English	
Page	327	
Publisher	Wiley-Blackwell; 2nd edition	
Publication date	January 26, 2004	
Language	English	
ISBN	1405113366	

2.2. Technique of Data Analysis

The technique of data analysis from this research used some steps. According to Hamzah (2020), "Data analysis is a systematic process of locating and collating data obtained from interviews, field notes, and other understandable materials. This research analyzed data through 3 steps. And, data were prepared and analyzed using data reduction, data display, and concluding.

3. Result and Discussion

This chapter presents the findings and discussion of the study referring to the proposed research problems. The data presented the answer to the research question "How did the researcher review the book English Pronunciation, Intonation, and Accent Reduction for Japanese Speakers book." The findings related to the review of the book about pronouncing English sounds.

3.1. Findings

3.1.1. Book Introduction

The title of the book is English Pronunciation, Intonation and Accent Reduction for Japanese Speakers by Peggy Tharpe, 2021. This book is insight for teachers and answers for students. Pronunciation teacher and accent reduction coach, Peggy Tharpe, M.A. TESOL, shares her insight and strategies for helping students with the specific challenges brought by their first language.

This book answered what helps Japanese speakers improve their sound in English and give unique strategies that have answered many puzzled teachers, frustrated students, and tutors. This book is suitable for teachers who want to teach English Pronunciation at formal institutions such as schools and also informal institutions.

The book was written by Peggy Tharpe and has 213 pages. A book with this thickness is not properly used to the full extent by students in junior and senior high school. It is more suitable for college students and teachers level, besides this book also has a quite difficult scientific language.

3.1.2. Book Outline

1. General view of the book

This book explained new pronunciation guides and online courses, and learn tips and techniques for teaching and learning English pronunciation, intonation, and accent reduction. There are seven chapters in this book which are getting ready terms that will use, how to speak in a stress-based language, mastering vowel sounds, separating R and L, other consonant sounds, managing groups of consonants, and intonation patterns.

The book discusses how the features of Japanese affect the pronunciation of American English, and talks about how the Japanese mode of articulation differs and practice the English mode. It also describes and compares the role of vowels in American English and Japanese and how to fine-tune and strengthen learners' consonant sounds. There is a lot to understand in each part about pronunciation in this book because this book has a quite difficult scientific language.

2. Book parts and chapters

This book has seven chapters that explain every part clearly. The writer also gave a short link to the video to learners about the material. There are seven parts in this book that the researcher explain in this part.

Part one: Getting Ready

In this section, four points explain symbols for sounds, resources and references, feedback, and how the sounds are made by your jaw, your lips, and your tongue. The first point which is a symbol for sounds explained how to use the international phonetic alphabet technique in teaching English pronunciation. This is a good tool for linguists. The procedure of technique is the teacher teaches the ways to spell the sound, for example :

a. Vowels:

ā = bait, bay, weight, wane

ē = beat, seed, relieve

æ = bat, mask, adequate

etc.

b. Consonants :

k = Kathy, Catherine, accord, accent

kw = quick, queen, quarter, question

θ = toothpaste, think

etc

The second point is *resources and references*. It recommends applications and websites on how to learn sound in English. There are seven applications which are Merriam-webster.com, sounds of speech app, englishclub.com, manythings.org, and playphrase.me, and Netflix.

The third point is *you will need feedback*. This point described that if the teacher or students make changes to produce the sounds, they should get feedback from the others, so we know whether to adjust the practice strategies. It is important need to know because finally making the sound well enough to be understood. The last point, is your jaw, your lips, and your tongue. It explains if the learners want to sound natural when speaking English, they should learn how to hold their mouth so the students can produce the sounds of English rather than the sounds of their first language. This point clarifies in detail how to hold your jaw, your tongue position, and lip exercise for English.

Part two: How to Speak in a Stress-based Language

In this part, there are seven points which are speaking a stress-based language, the sound prints of your spoken word, stress and duration, mastering syllable stress, using little schwas to accentuate stress patterns, rate, and late endings, and the last is -cian, -sion, -tion endings.

Part three: Mastering Vowel Sounds

In this part, there are ten points which are Japanese vs English vowels, the vowels in beat and bit, powerful ae, letter mixups and reductions, the difference between bet, bait and bat, the sounds of O, UH vs AH, Ü AND Ū SOUNDS, the different ER IR UR, and the last is vowel + ER.

Part four: Separating R and L

There are five points in this part, they are R and L, dark L, final R, strengthen R and L, and last about adjectives and adverbs with L plus R.

Part five: Other Consonant Sounds

There are eighteen points in this part, which are final N, N vs NG, twin pairs of consonants, why T changes to D, the invasive O after T and D sounds, S and Z, S that sounds like TH, the different CH J ZH S Z, the different S, Z, T, D before E and I, consonant mixups, finals –s and signal –ed, TH sounds, H and F, W and Y, QU = KW, and the last is B vs V.

Part six: Managing Groups of Consonants

This part has five points which are consonant clusters, the different BL-BR, CL-CR, PL-PR, GL-GR, S consonant clusters, final clusters, and the last disappearing syllables.

Part seven: Intonation Patterns

There are four points in this part, they are questions vs statements, responsive intonation, widening your pitch range, and last summing up.

3.1.3. Highlight Part of The Book

The main book "English Pronunciation, Intonation, and Accent Reduction for Japanese Speaker" by Peggy Tharpe M.A. TESOL is compared with the book "The Pronunciation of English" by Charles W. Kreidler. Both books aim to help non-native English speakers improve their pronunciation skills. This part compares the plot, writing styles, strengths, and weaknesses of 2 books "The Pronunciation of English" by Charles W. Kreidler (2004) and "English Pronunciation, Intonation, and Accent Reduction for Japanese Speaker" by Peggy Tharpe M.A. TESOL (2021).

Firstly, it's important to note that the two books have different focuses. "The Pronunciation of English" is a comprehensive guide to the sounds of English, their articulation, and the rules governing their use. It is aimed at linguists, language teachers, and advanced learners of English who want to gain a deeper understanding of the language's pronunciation. In contrast, "English Pronunciation, Intonation and Accent Reduction for Japanese Speakers" is designed specifically for Japanese speakers who want to improve their pronunciation, intonation, and accent when speaking English. In this part, the researcher described seven chapters in the book English Pronunciation, Intonation, and Accent Reduction for Japanese Speakers compare with the book The English Pronunciation.

Chapter 1: Symbol for sounds

In summary, both books cover the topic of symbols for sounds, but "English Pronunciation, Intonation and Accent Reduction for Japanese Speaker" has a specific chapter dedicated to introducing the IPA and its symbols, while "The Pronunciation of English" uses IPA symbols throughout the text to represent the sounds of English, without a specific chapter devoted to the topic.

Chapter 2: How to Speak in a stress-based language

In summary, both books cover the topic of stress and rhythm in English, but "English Pronunciation, Intonation and Accent Reduction for Japanese Speaker" has a specific chapter devoted to it and is tailored to Japanese speakers, while "The Pronunciation of English" covers it as part of a broader exploration of English pronunciation and provides a more comprehensive understanding of the topic.

Chapter 3: Mastering vowel sounds

In short, both books cover the topic of mastering vowel sounds in English, but "English Pronunciation, Intonation and Accent Reduction for Japanese Speaker" provides a more targeted and practical approach with a specific chapter and exercises, while "The Pronunciation of English" provides a more comprehensive and theoretical exploration of English vowel sounds within its broader coverage of English pronunciation.

Chapter 4: Separating R and L

In brief, both books cover the topic of separating the sounds of "R" and "L" in English pronunciation, but "English Pronunciation, Intonation and Accent Reduction for Japanese Speaker" provides a more targeted and practical approach with a specific chapter and exercises, while "The Pronunciation of English" includes the topic as part of its broader coverage of English pronunciation and provides more detailed explanations of the sounds and their articulation.

Chapter 5: Other Consonant Sounds

In terms of the level of detail and approach, "English Pronunciation, Intonation and Accent Reduction for Japanese Speaker" provides a more targeted and practical approach with specific chapters on different consonant sounds, while "The Pronunciation of English" includes the topic as part of its broader coverage of English pronunciation and provides a more comprehensive explanation of different consonant sounds. "The Pronunciation of English" may be more suitable for learners who want a more thorough understanding of English pronunciation, while "English Pronunciation, Intonation and Accent Reduction for Japanese Speaker" may be more suitable for learners who want to focus on specific sounds that are particularly challenging for Japanese speakers.

Chapter 6: Managing Groups of Consonants

While both books cover aspects of English pronunciation, intonation, and accent reduction, "English Pronunciation, Intonation, and Accent Reduction for Japanese Speakers" by Peggy Tharpe focuses specifically on the needs of Japanese speakers learning English, with a focus on managing consonant sounds, while "The Pronunciation of English" by Charles W. Kreidler is a more general guide to English pronunciation, covering a wider range of topics related to phonetics and phonology.

Chapter 7: Intonation Patterns

In brief, while both books cover intonation patterns, Peggy Tharpe's book is specifically targeted at Japanese speakers who are learning English as a second language, providing exercises and practice activities to help improve their intonation patterns. Charles W. Kreidler's book is a more comprehensive guide to English pronunciation, covering a wider

range of topics related to phonetics and phonology, including intonation patterns as they appear across different English dialects.

The second highlight part of the book, in terms of writing style, both books are well-written and easy to follow. "The Pronunciation of English" is a more academic text, with a focus on theory and technical details. It contains numerous examples, diagrams, and exercises to help readers practice their pronunciation. On the other hand, "English Pronunciation, Intonation and Accent Reduction for Japanese Speakers" has a more practical approach, with a focus on providing specific tips and strategies for Japanese speakers to improve their English pronunciation. It also includes audio resources to help learners hear and practice correct pronunciation

Then, in terms of strengths, "The Pronunciation of English" is praised for its depth of coverage, providing a detailed analysis of English phonetics and phonology. It is a valuable resource for language teachers and linguists who want to gain a deeper understanding of the subject. In contrast, "English Pronunciation, Intonation and Accent Reduction for Japanese Speakers" is a practical and user-friendly guide that provides specific advice and exercises to help Japanese speakers improve their English pronunciation. The writer also gives applications and online links related to the material. This book, besides this, is the new book in 2021, it is written for Japanese speakers because it explained the difference in sound between English and Japanese, but it is still relevant to other Asia students and teachers including Indonesia.

The last is the terms of weaknesses. Some readers may find "The Pronunciation of English" to be too technical and theoretical, with a focus on academic research rather than practical application. Additionally, it may be challenging for beginners to grasp the concepts presented in the book without prior knowledge of phonetics and phonology. On the other hand, "English Pronunciation, Intonation and Accent Reduction for Japanese Speakers" is designed specifically for Japanese speakers, so it may not be as helpful for learners from other language backgrounds. This book may be too technical for readers who do not have a background in phonetics or linguistics. It is also more focused on pronunciation aspects rather than overall language acquisition, so the readers may need to seek other sources to strengthen their English language skills as a whole.

In short, both "The Pronunciation of English" and "English Pronunciation, Intonation and Accent Reduction for Japanese Speaker" are valuable resources for learners of English who want to improve their pronunciation. The former is a comprehensive guide to English phonetics and phonology, while the latter provides practical advice and exercises for Japanese speakers. The choice between the two books ultimately depends on the reader's level of English proficiency, their specific learning goals, and their background knowledge of English phonetics and phonology.

3.1.4. Book Evaluation

The content of "English Pronunciation, Intonation and Accent Reduction for Japanese Speakers" by Peggy Tharpe is well-organized and thorough. The author covers the basics of English pronunciation, explains the differences between Japanese and English pronunciation, and provides numerous strategies and techniques for improving pronunciation, intonation, and accent. The book also includes exercises and practice drills to help readers apply what they have learned. Overall, the content is comprehensive and practical and should be very helpful for Japanese speakers who are looking to improve their English pronunciation.

Next, for the reader's needs, this book is specifically targeted toward Japanese speakers who are looking to improve their English pronunciation, intonation, and accent. As such, it is well-suited to meet the needs of this audience. The author does an excellent job of explaining the differences between Japanese and English pronunciation and provides strategies and techniques that are tailored to the needs of Japanese speakers. Additionally, the book includes plenty of examples and practice exercises, which should help readers apply what they have learned and improve their pronunciation skills. Format: The book is available in both paperback and Kindle formats, which should make it accessible to a wide range of readers. Then, the layout of the book is clear and easy to follow. It included headings, subheadings, and bullet points to help readers navigate the content. The book also includes numerous diagrams and illustrations, which should be helpful for readers who are visual learners.

3.2. Discussion

Teaching pronunciation is important to improve students' understanding in the field of segmental and suprasegmental pronunciation. Therefore, it is necessary to have a form of pronunciation teaching to improve teacher and student understanding. In learning the basics of pronunciation, the teacher will not only teach speaking comfortably but also improve their listening comprehension when native speakers speak. At the same time, pronunciation is important to improve the students' speaking ability to communicate with others.

Based on the findings of this study, this study aimed to present research questions that have been answered because of the results of this study. To answer the research question, the researcher conducted descriptive qualitative research with library research to review a book related to pronouncing English sounds. The data source of this research was a book. Based on the research question, "How did the researcher review the book English Pronunciation, Intonation, and Accent Reduction for Japanese Speakers book?"

The title of the book is English Pronunciation, Intonation and Accent Reduction for Japanese Speakers by Peggy Tharpe, 2021. The description of this book is insight for teachers and answers for students. Pronunciation teacher and accent reduction coach, Peggy Tharpe, M.A. TESOL, shares her insight and strategies for helping students with the specific challenges brought by their first language. This book answered what helps Japanese speakers improve their sound in English and give unique strategies that have answered many puzzled teachers, frustrated students, and tutors.

This book explained new pronunciation guides and online courses, and learn tips and techniques for teaching and learning English pronunciation, intonation, and accent reduction. There are seven parts, which are getting ready terms that will use, how to speak in a stress-based language, mastering vowel sounds, separating R and L, other consonant sounds, managing groups of consonants, and intonation patterns.

There are four stages of writing a book review which is introducing the book, outlining the content of the book, highlighting parts of the book, and evaluating the book. First, about the introduction, the book explains about outlines the general topic, indicates who the book is for, and places the book in its field. Second, outline the content of the book describe give a general view of its organization, and state the topic of each chapter or section. Third, highlight parts of the book. This step about the reviewer to select particular chapters or themes for evaluation, and critique the argument of the book. The last, evaluate the book. This part focused to comment on aspects of the content, indicating how it meets the readers'

needs, and remarking on its format, price, and value for money. The reviewer also makes recommendations for purchase or otherwise.

In this research, the main book the title "English Pronunciation, Intonation, and Accent Reduction for Japanese Speaker" by Peggy Tharpe M.A. TESOL, and then compare with the book "The Pronunciation of English" by Charles W. Kreidler. Both books aim to help non-native English speakers improve their pronunciation skills.

4. Conclusion and Recommendation

Based on the findings and discussion of this research, it can be concluded that the book English Pronunciation, Intonation, and Accent Reduction for Japanese Speakers is a good recommendation for teaching English pronunciation to students. It explained new pronunciation guides and online courses, and learn tips and techniques for teaching and learning English pronunciation, intonation, and accent reduction. There are four stages of writing a book review, outlining the content of the book, highlighting parts of the book, and evaluating the book. The content of "English Pronunciation, Intonation and Accent Reduction for Japanese Speakers" by Peggy Tharpe is well-organized and thorough. The author covers the basics of English pronunciation, explains the differences between Japanese and English pronunciation, and provides numerous strategies and techniques for improving pronunciation, intonation, and accent. The book also includes plenty of exercises in the form of links to videos and practice drills to help readers apply what they have learned. Overall, the content is comprehensive and practical and should be very helpful for Japanese speakers who are looking to improve their English pronunciation.

The researcher realizes that this research is far from being perfect. Mistakes and weaknesses still happen in many aspects such as methods, analyses, and discussion. Positive suggestions and criticism still researchers need to make the next study better. The researcher would like to suggest to the teacher that this book is a good recommendation for teaching English pronunciation to students. For the next researcher, the result of this research is expected to be useful for future researchers as a reference to conduct further research. Positive criticism is needed to make the next study better.

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